

GPM2220000811: peptide model: 18782.1.1 of ENSMUSP0000064155

ENSMUSP0000064155: Rif1.p, no protein text annotation available

Sample information

#	log(e)	log(l)	m+h	delta	z	sequence
18782	-12.4	4.19	2081.9846	0.0047	2/2	vvar ¹³⁸⁶ TEQIVNEDSQAAALAPNPK ¹⁴⁰⁴ tlrr (5980) 0.035

mods: S1394+Phospho, K1404+Label:+6 Da

CGItemp33452 scan 18782 (charge 2)

matched/total: # ions: 66% intensity: 84% μ : 0.01, σ : 0.10 Da

bond	+1 _y	+1 _y -17	+1 _y -18	+1 _b	+1 _b -17	+1 _b -18
T ₁	1980.937	1963.910	1962.926	102.055	85.028	84.044
E ₂	+21851.894	1834.868	1833.884	231.098	214.071	213.087
Q ₃	1723.836	1706.809	1705.825	359.156	342.130	341.146
I ₄	1610.752	1593.725	1592.741	472.240	455.214	454.230
V ₅	1511.683	1494.657	1493.673	571.309	554.282	553.298
N ₆	1397.640	1380.614	1379.630	685.352	668.325	667.341
E ₇	1268.598	1251.571	1250.587	814.394	797.368	796.384
D ₈	1153.571	1136.544	1135.560	929.421	912.395	911.411
S ₉	986.572	969.546	968.562	1096.419	1079.393	1078.409
Q ₁₀	858.514	841.487	840.503	1224.478	1207.451	1206.467
A ₁₁	787.477	770.450	769.466	1295.515	1278.489	1277.505
A ₁₂	716.440	699.413	698.429	1366.552	1349.526	1348.542
A ₁₃	645.403	628.376	627.392	1437.589	1420.563	1419.579
L ₁₄	532.318	515.292	514.308	1550.673	1533.647	1532.663
A ₁₅	461.281	444.255	443.271	1621.711	1604.684	1603.700
P ₁₆	364.229	347.202	346.218	1718.763	1701.737	1700.753
N ₁₇	250.186	233.159	232.175	1832.806	1815.780	1814.796
P ₁₈	153.133	136.106	135.122	1929.859	1912.832	1911.848

Other observed ions:

Ion type	m/z	Ion type	m/z
by[15-19]	514.308	by[4-8]	571.272
b[7]-H ₃ PO ₄	716.394	γ [19]-H ₃ PO ₄ ⁺²	992.496
ay[6-15]	1023.414	(parent-2H ₂ O) ⁺²	1023.485
b[13]-H ₃ PO ₄	1339.589	by[7-19]	1379.630
b[14]-H ₃ PO ₄	1452.673	b[14]-H ₃ PO ₄	1452.673
b[15]-H ₃ PO ₄	1523.711		

Residue modification sets tested:

- Complete mods:**
 - i. Carbamidomethyl@C, Label:+6 Da@K, Label:+6 Da@R
- Potential mods:**
 - i. Oxidation@M, Phospho@S, Phospho@T, Phospho@Y
 - ii. Oxidation@M, Oxidation@W, Deamidated@N, Deamidated@Q
 - iii. Dioxidation@M, Dioxidation@W
- Protein-specific PTMs:**
 - i. Phospho@S, Phospho@Y, Phospho@T, Acetyl@K
- N-terminal:**
 - i. Ammonia-loss@Q, Ammonia-loss@C, Dehydrated@E (peptide)
 - ii. ragged, Acetyl (protein)

E-value calculation:

